

Integrating a Zero-Trust Adaptive Security Framework in Edge based Federated Learning

Paul Shepherd
London South Bank University
Instituto de Telecomunicações
paul@av.it.pt

Tasos Dagiuklas
London South Bank University
tdagiuklas@lsbu.ac.uk

Bugra Alkan
London South Bank University
alkanb@lsbu.ac.uk

Jonathan Rodriguez
Instituto de Telecomunicações
Aveiro, Portugal
jonathan@av.it.pt

Abstract—Federated Learning (FL) allows multiple clients to collaboratively train a machine learning model without sharing their raw data, thus addressing privacy data concerns. The joint application of FL (Federated Learning) and MEC (Multi-Access Edge Computing) enables efficient utilization of computation and storage resources at the edge. By deploying the FL model at the edge, data are trained locally on the device or edge node, reducing latency, and facilitating real-time processing and decision-making, whilst also ensuring data privacy. However, the decentralized FL is subject to security and trust challenges, since MEC data may get poisoned. Therefore, ensuring the trustworthiness of clients is pivotal to ensure integrity and performance of FL models. This paper presents an adaptive Zero Trust framework which assumes no inherent trust in any client, is based on continuously verifying and validating the clients' behavior, to ensure that only reliable contributors (clients) are incorporated in the global model aggregation.

Keywords— Zero Trust, Federated Learning, Mobile Edge Computing, privacy, machine learning,

I. INTRODUCTION

In this paper we aim to demonstrate an innovative approach designed to contribute to the privacy, integrity, and performance of Federated Learning (FL) systems by incorporating a trust evaluation mechanism [1].

Despite the considerable progress in FL and edge computing, there are still gaps [2] in existing knowledge that need to be addressed. Firstly, is the lack of comprehensive techniques for data verification and validation in FL that can address the challenges of data privacy and data quality in FL while maintaining scalability and feasibility [3]. And secondly, the limited understanding of the practical challenges of implementing FL and edge computing techniques in real-world settings, where data could be compromised [4] [5].

The proposed approach builds on the literature to implement a trust framework based on the the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model architecture, MADM (Multi-Attribute Decision Making) and, (TOPSIS) Technique for Order Preference by Similarity [6],[7] to an Ideal Solution technique, that obtains a trust level based on the weighted sum of specific metrics related to AUC (The Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve) [8], by plotting the true positive rate (TPR) against the false positive rate (FPR) at various threshold levels, providing a single measure of the model's discriminatory attribute. Aggregate Trust Score Scaling System (ATSSS) to ensure an efficient model training by adaptively adjusting the weights and trust scores of clients based on their performance metrics. A key feature of the FL process is the omission of clients with low trust scores, hence maintaining the integrity and performance of the FL process.

II. The frameworks key components

A mechanism to simulate the presence of adversarial clients by incorporating poisoned data through random label flipping has been developed. Each client is assigned a probability of being adversarial, set at 0.5, meaning there is a

50% chance that any given client will behave maliciously. If a client is chosen to be adversarial, it will flip a portion of its training labels based on a specified probability ranging from 0.1 to 0.9. This label flipping distorts the training data, effectively "poisoning" the dataset. The proportion of labels to be flipped is determined by the FLIP_PERCENTAGE parameter, while the likelihood of a client engaging in this behavior is dictated by the FLIP_PROBABILITY parameter. This adversarial behavior is configured through environment variables in the Docker Compose setup environment, ensuring that each client's behavior is probabilistically determined at runtime. By implementing this setup, the impact of poisoned data on the FL process has been studied and the robustness and resilience of the model training against such adversarial attacks has been evaluated.

The Multi-Attribute Decision-Making (MADM) techniques and the TOPSIS method are implemented to evaluate and rank MEC nodes based on the performance metrics, namely accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, AUC, and ATSSS. These metrics are combined using a weighted scheme, allowing for a trust score calculation that adapts to the evolving performance and behavior of clients. The trust scores are continuously updated enabling a real-time response to any detected anomalies. The proposed Trust Adjustment Mechanism, or weighting scheme, ensures that each of the metrics are proportional to its relevance on each training round. To calculate the trust score, a weighted linear regression formula is used:

$$\text{Trust Score} = w_1 \cdot \text{Accuracy} + w_2 \cdot \text{Precision} + w_3 \cdot \text{Recall} + w_4 \cdot \text{F1 Score} + w_5 \cdot \text{AUC-ROC} + w_6 \cdot \text{ATSSS}$$

The Trust Score calculation applies the MADM technique, where TOPSIS is specifically used to rank MEC nodes based on their trustworthiness. TOPSIS is a MADM method that ranks options according to the Euclidean Principle - based on their distance to an ideal solution; where we refer to anti-ideal solution as the worst possible performance. The aim is to select the MEC nodes that are closest to the ideal solution/farthest away from the anti-ideal solution. After calculating the relative "closeness" for all clients, a threshold is applied to determine which clients to omit from the training process before model aggregation. By omitting clients with trust scores below the threshold, the FL model benefits from improved accuracy, increased robustness, and faster convergence.

III. NUMERICAL RESULTS

The Flower framework (Fig.1) has been chosen to facilitate a secure and efficient communication platform among decentralized devices and the coordination and aggregation of the global model [9].

The architecture and deployment involve configuring tasks on both the MEC nodes and server. Each MEC node has a unique dataset, along with model, hyper-parameters, and training methods. Global computation oversees the entire learning process on the server without knowledge of

individual client data. The data loader handles the loading and preprocessing of training data, including the intentional flipping of a portion of labels to simulate adversarial behavior. The architecture and deployment involve configuring tasks on both the MEC nodes and server.

Fig.1. Flower core framework architecture with both Virtual Client Engine and Edge Client Engine (<https://flower.ai/> / <https://github.com/adap/flower>)

The LSTM model architecture is used for training, together with the averaging algorithm FedAvg. The trust scores are updated after each training round to reflect the latest client performance metrics. The client selection and omission process is managed by the central server, which filters out and omits clients with low trust scores to ensure that only reliable contributions are considered.

The experiment was carried out using the Flower Framework and its components, simulating 10 MEC nodes over 5 iterative rounds. The performance evaluation in the presence and absence of adversaries (label flipping) is given by Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Iterations - shows both none and label flipping

The evaluation Loss is consistent across all clients at 0.3046, indicating that the average loss during the evaluation was stable. The Evaluation Accuracy was also consistent, showing an accuracy of 0.8409 for all clients. The AUC metric was approx. 0.9716 across all clients, suggesting a high probability to distinguish between positive and negative classes. The Precision was 0.7843 for all clients, indicating a relatively high ratio of true positive identifications among all positive identifications. Moreover, the Recall is uniformly high at 0.9808, demonstrating strong capability to identify nearly all positive cases. The F1 Score balances precision and recall, providing a single metric that reflects both false positives and false negatives. The F1 is 0.8716, showing a balance between precision and recall, suggesting effective performance across all clients.

The ATSSS Score varied slightly among clients, ranging from 0.8457 to 0.8514, demonstrating the model's ability to assess and maintain stable performance. Finally, the Trust Score varied among clients, with scores around 0.6509 to 0.6795, indicating moderate to high trust in the model's prediction capability during the evaluation. Overall, the model demonstrates strong and consistent performance across multiple evaluation metrics.

The performance evaluation with adversaries (with label flipping Fig. 2.) where we assume data flipping probability of 0.1 - 0.9, and a probability of a client being adversary of 0.5. In this context, the Evaluation Loss is 0.3589, suggests that the model's predictions are close to the actual values, indicating a good fit on the validation data. The Evaluation Accuracy is 84.08% indicating that the model correctly classifies about 84% of the instances. The AUC is high at 0.9555, indicating excellent model performance in distinguishing between the classes. It suggests that the model has a high true positive rate and a low false positive rate. The Precision is 0.7904, suggesting that when the model predicts an intrusion, it is correct about 79% of the time. The Recall is approx. 0.9673, indicating that the model captures about 97% of the actual intrusions. The F1 Score is given by 0.8699 that shows good performance. The ATSSS average is 0.84, showing consistent performance across different clients. Finally, the Trust Score varied from 0.61 to 0.67, showing variability among clients, possibly indicating differences in data quality or model performance consistency.

The FL approach for the IDS (Intrusion Detection Systems) model shows robust and consistent performance across multiple clients, with high recall and AUC scores demonstrating its effectiveness in detecting intrusions, where a total of 3 out of the 10 clients were omitted before model aggregation.

IV. Conclusion

This research aims to present a novel trust evaluation framework for FL, incorporating Zero Trust principles to achieve privacy, security, and enhanced performance. The proposed implementation has shown proof of concept to provide a robust, deployable, and scalable approach to trust management in FL, by ensuring that only trustworthy clients contribute to model training. By adjusting the threshold for client inclusion based on their relative closeness to an ideal solution, the FL system maintains high model performance and security. Given that the proposed framework is still in early development it has shown to effectively evaluate client trustworthiness, dynamically adjust trust scores, and omit low-trust clients.

Future work aims to address scalability and convergence performance where we would expect to observe consistent adversary detection, and improved model accuracy, convergence speed, and robustness.

REFERENCES

- [1] Wei Yang B Lim, Chunyan. et al. doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1909.11875
- [2] A. Blanco-Justicia, K. Tan. et al. doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2021.104468
- [3] A. Wainakh, Max Mühlhäuser, et al. doi.org/10.3390/s23010031
- [4] Aaqib, M., Ali, A., Chen, L. et al. doi.org/10.1186/s13677-023-00416-8
- [5] Ibrahim, Y Kashmoola. et al. doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-8059-5_36
- [6] C Radulescu, M Radulescu doi.org/10.3390/electronics13040789
- [7] Bader Alojaiman doi.org/10.3390/pr11051313
- [8] Z. Yang et al., doi: 10.1109/TPAMI.2023.3303943
- [9] Daniel Beutel, Nicholas Lane, et al. doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2007.14390

*Repository <https://github.com/FLZeroTrust/Framework>